

MANUFACTURING OF THERMOPLASTIC TITANIUM DIOXIDE REINFORCED NANOCOMPOSITES BY TWIN SCREW EXTRUSION

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SUMMARY

This study presents a theoretical description and simulation in combination with an experimental examination of processing conditions for generating nanoparticle reinforced thermoplastic polymers. Different screw configurations and processing steps were investigated and optimized to obtain deagglomerated and well distributed particles inside the thermoplastic matrix and so gaining improved mechanical properties. Experimental values are correlated with theoretical simulations.

Keywords: Processing, extrusion, nanocomposites, spherical inorganic nanoparticles, simulation

INTRODUCTION

Processing conditions are one of the key issues, which have to be examined and optimized to gain enhanced performance of nanoparticles filled thermoplastic materials. This fact is based on the inclination of nanoparticles to form agglomerates, which have to be broken down to singular particles during processing. The bonding mechanisms which may occur between inorganic nanoparticles are interlocking (non-spherical particles), electrostatic (conductible materials), van der Waals' forces and of course liquid or solid bridging (sintering, solid diffusion). In our case, where spherical, non-conductive titanium dioxide (TiO₂, 15 nm) particles had been used van der Waals' forces play the most important role.

The process of agglomerate breakdown forming singular particles is termed dispersion. In polymer compounding, such as twin screw extrusion, this can be achieved through three steps [1]:

- initial wetting of the clustered particle structures by polymer melt,
- displacing air at the particle-melt interface
- permitting mechanical energy to be applied in order to overcome the interparticle forces

If these forces are in excess of some threshold value, determined by the bonding characteristics of the particles, deagglomeration occurs. An analysis of forces, which are necessary to deagglomerate the nanoparticles, can be made in view of one single agglomerate, which is existent in form of a rigid dumbbell, consisting of two particles with equal radii r (Figure 1). This agglomerate is placed in a homogeneous velocity

field of an incompressible Newtonian fluid. If the two beads are in contact with one another, the maximum separating force (F_{\max}) is obtained when the dumbbell orientation is 45° to the direction of shear, being proportional to the shear stress τ ($\mu \dot{\gamma}$) and the product r^2 (Formula 1). One can say, that the less force is required to break apart combinations of larger beads than smaller ones and that dispersive mixing is enhanced under conditions of high shear stress. Therefore, the degree of deagglomeration is highly dependent on the generated shear stresses inside the screw channel. The shear stresses can be correlated with the specific application of energy e (Formula 2). It can be summed up that the higher the shear stress the higher is the specific allocation of energy and the higher is the degree of Deagglomeration [1].

Figure 1: Analysis of forces which are necessary for agglomeration break up

This study contains a systematic approach to develop optimized processing conditions for nanoparticle reinforced polyamide with a co-rotating twin screw extruder (Berstorff GmbH, ZE 25 x 44). Several screw configurations with varying energy input and differing processing steps (e.g. single and multi pass processing) were investigated to reveal, which specific application of energy can be achieved and how this results in deagglomerated and well distributed nanoparticles.

Therefore, the important distribution quality of nanosized particles and fracture mechanisms are shown in high resolution SEM pictures. The measured experimental values of specific application of energy are correlated with theoretical simulations.

As a result optimized processing conditions were used to generate highly mechanically improved nanocomposite properties.

EXPERIMENTS

Extrusion Process Development

The incorporation of nanoparticles into polyamide 66 (PA 66, Schulamid MV2, Schulman GmbH) matrix was realized by a co-rotating twin screw extruder (ZE25x44, Berstorff GmbH) with 10 heating barrels. The dried polymer granulate was fed via gravimetric high-precision feeder (K-tron GmbH) through the main hopper and the side feeder into the barrel of the machine. Contrary to traditional feeding of particles the feeding of the used titanium dioxide nanoparticles (7 Vol.-%, TiO₂, RM 300, Sachtleben Chemie GmbH) directly into the main hopper showed very promising results in preliminary tests and was applied in the actual process development.

During this research work two processing steps were differed: single and multi pass extrusion. Important processing parameters are temperature profile of the barrels, throughput and screw rotation speed. An important process property is the inserted energy, depending on torque and screw speed. The torque is a function of the viscosity of the materials and the screw setup. The used screw setups for single pass extrusion are drawn schematically in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Screw configurations, which had been used for single pass extrusion

All screws offer the same plastification zone. An intensive mixing is realized with screw E1, where three dispersive and entirely filled mixing zones are generated. This configuration applies high shearing to the polymer and nanoparticles.

After inserting particles with the use of screw configuration E1 and so creating a nanoparticles containing masterbatch (7 Vol.-% TiO₂) a second extrusion was carried out with screw configuration M1 (multi-pass extrusion). This screw set up contains reduced dispersive zone but owes a distinctive distributive mixing zone to homogenize the particles in the matrix.

The charpy impact energy was analyzed according to DIN EN ISO 179 using a pendulum-type impact tester.

Simulation of the extrusion process via Sigma Simulation Software [2]

As input parameters to simulate the process behavior of twin screw extrusion material characteristics, process parameters and geometric variables are necessary. Existing models are used for reasonable mapping of the process. These reveal e.g. residence time or residence time distribution, dispersion capacity of screw configuration and melting behavior. Nowadays for all of these factors calculating models are available. A reasonable mathematical description of processing with the help of independent process models can only be achieved if interactions between them are considered (Figure 3).

The material characteristics are divided into rheological properties, thermodynamic units and densities. Rheology of polymer melt can be described ether with Carreau-WLF-law or with power law.

Process parameters depict screw speed, trough-put, cylinder temperatures etc. While simulation it has to be considered that the used models assume constant geometric variables as well as boundary conditions. These are not given for the extruder as a whole along the screw and cylinder configuration because of interaction between differing functional and temperature zones. Therefore for simulation the extruder is divided in sections of same geometric variables and boundary conditions. Till a number of 100 sections is reached a bisection of each longest zones takes place. In this way a fine discretization with non-constant zone length is generated.

Figure 3: Interactions between process models and resulting process parameters

To achieve a passable calculation period each model is computed separated, but to gain interactions between the rheological and thermodynamic parameters iteration loops are fulfilled (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Order of events in SIGMA

RESULTS

Simulation of extrusion process for a dispersive screw configuration

Deagglomeration is essential for generating enhancements of mechanical properties. Simulation of the incorporation step of nanoparticles into polymer by using an intensive dispersive screw configuration depicts the effectiveness of each zone.

Simulation of specific energy input is depicted for screw configuration E1 in Figure 5. To gain a better understanding of the processes – dispersion and distribution –, which go on inside the extrusion machine, an examination of the specific energy input is from great advance. The engine power P correlates at constant trough-put m with the specific energy e ($P/m = e$). This value is an output of the extruder, but depicts the over-all energy input of the machine and not single element energy of the differing zones. Element energy apportions the single zones, which are crucial for deagglomeration. Therefore the energy performance is simulated via SIGMA simulation software for all

specific zones and sections of screw set-up. One can see that the calculated over-all value is in very good agreement with the output value of the extruder (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Run of the element power and the cumulated power along the screw length of screw configuration E1 containing a sharp dispersive zone for polyamide 66 containing 7 vol.-% titanium dioxide

By having a closer look at the energy input of single screw elements it becomes clearly visible, that the main shearing energy input into the polymer/particle system takes place during melting of the polymer granulate in the melting zone just after feeding the machine. The special configured dispersion zone implies just a marginal shearing input into the system.

Literature shows that editing process of thermoplastic polymers is mainly influenced by plastification. At this the quality of dispersion is defined through melting zone, in which high energy input appears [3]. Up to 80 % of the total mechanical energy input of the twin screw extruder takes place inside the plastification zone [4]. These statements excellently affirm the findings gained through our simulation, where 81% of the total power is inserted inside the melting zone. One can therefore infer from this result, that high energy input in the plastification zone is the essential key factor for deagglomeration at multi pass extrusion.

A further lay out design of dispersive zones seems not to be targeting for nanoparticles reinforced thermoplastics. At single pass extrusion in this common way neither the specific energy nor the residence time can be adequate improved to overcome the high adhesion forced of the particles.

For this reason it is questionable if a reproduction of the melting zone over the screw length could not improve the specific energy input.

Single pass extrusion via reproduction of the melting zone

To insert granulates over the main feeder (MF) as well as over the side feeder (SF) a new screw configuration E2 was built up (see Figure 2). Here the melting zone of screw configuration E1 is replicated twice over the screw length. Several process combinations are from interest:

- Addition of granulate over MF and SF1 at a ratio of 70/30
- Addition of granulate over MF, SF1 and SF2
- Addition of granulate over MF and SF1 (70/30) at lowered cylinder temperatures

If one feeds the twin screw extruder with granulate over the main feeder and at the same time over the first side feeder in a ration of 70/30, this process management results in a significant enhancement of element power inside the second and third melting zone (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Run of the element power and the cumulated power along the screw length of screw configuration E2 with inserting granulate via MF and SF1 for polyamide 66 containing 7 vol.-% titanium dioxide

Simulation of this operation clearly depicts this result and affirms the advisement, that existence of not molten granulates inside the extruder is responsible for an improvement of the power entry.

If one examines the over-all power P it can be detected that the simulated value of $P_{\text{simulated}} = 2.91 \text{ kW}$ is of good approximation with the measured power of $P_{\text{measured}} = 2.80 \text{ kW}$. In comparison to screw configuration E1 and the common processing this kind of processing leads to a small improvement of the energy input. The over-all power input of screw configuration E1 is $P_{\text{simulated}} = 2.71 \text{ kW}$ while the

energy input of screw configuration E2 (addition of granulate over MF and SF1) is $P_{\text{simulated}} = 2.91 \text{ kW}$.

The high energy input inside the third melting zone is caused by the not molten granulate, which was implemented through the first side feeder. This is affirmed through simulation of melting behaviour (see Figure 7). The screw is filled with solid till the end of the third melting zone.

Figure 7: Melting profile along the screw length of screw configuration E2 with inserting granulate via MF and SF1 for polyamide 66 containing 7 vol.-% titanium dioxide

This improved power input manifests also in the toughness of the produced nanocomposites. The impact toughness of notched specimens produced with screw configuration E1 (common process: addition of granulate only over MF) results for a 7 vol.-% nanoparticle containing polyamide 66 in 1.42 kJ/mm^2 while with the insertion of granulate via MF and SF1 an enhancement to 2.4 kJ/mm^2 can be achieved. However, this value is still underneath the value of pure polyamide 66: 3.03 kJ/mm^2 .

The estimation of agglomeration size via scanning electron microscopy against granulate feeding positions is shown in Figure 8. There are no significant changes in deagglomeration visible.

If the addition of granulates takes place not only over the main feeder (MF) but over side feeder 1 (SF1) as well as side feeder 2 (SF2) in ratio 70/15/15 no improvement of the cumulated power input is visible. The over-all energy input amounts up to 2.8 kW , which is comparable with the value for granulate feeding over MF and SF1 only.

Figure 8: Polished specimens for evaluation of agglomeration size caused by differing granulate feeding for polyamide 66 containing 7 vol.-% titanium dioxide

As a third variation granulate is fed via main feeder (MF) and side feeder 1 (SF1) going ahead with an extreme reduction of cylinder temperature after SF1 and SF2 from 260°C to 180°C. This means, that the second and third melting zone exhibit temperatures, which are extensively below the melting temperature of polyamide 66. Caused by this proceeding a high enhancement of melt viscosity happens, which affects the over-all energy input positively and results in a cumulated power of $P_{\text{simulated}} = 3.9 \text{ kW}$.

Figure 9 depicts polished surfaces done by scanning electron microscopy for with multi pass extrusion generated and dispersed masterbatch (feeding of nanoparticles over MF, screw configuration E1 and M1) in comparison to single pass extruded masterbatch where the granulate was fed over MF and SF1 at reduced cylinder temperature. The combinations of not molten granulate and enhancement of viscosity caused by temperature reduction lead at single passes extrusion to a very good deagglomeration of particles. The size of agglomerates is comparable to those gained from multi pass extrusion after the second extrusion step. Just the number seems to be little enhanced.

Therefore, single pass extrusion reaches almost the results of multi pass extrusion.

Figure 9: Polished specimens for evaluation of agglomeration size caused by multi pass and single pass extrusion for polyamide 66 containing 7 vol.-% titanium dioxide

Picture 10 shows the comparison of gained impact energy for with 7 vol.-% TiO₂-filled nanocomposites, which were processed in differing ways.

It becomes clearly visible, that the multi pass extrusion still offers the best toughness values.

Figure 10: Comparison of charpy impact toughness for polyamide 66 containing 7 vol.-% titanium dioxide at differing extrusion processes

CONCLUSIONS

Via simulation of the extrusion process it could be shown that the plastification zone implements the highest shearing energy into the particle/matrix-system. Therefore it was attempt to reproduce the plastification zone several times. The following simulation depicted, that die feeding of granulate via main feeder and side feeder 1 leads to a significant improvement of the element power in the melting zones, but the over-all power input was unchanged in comparison to just feeding the granulate over the main feeder and so there was no enhancement of the property profile. An additional temperature reduction at the melting zones resulted into high viscosity and a high specific energy input. Deagglomertion is almost comparable with the one resulting out of multi extrusion processing; only the number of agglomerate is slightly enhanced. This is the reason why toughness is reduced in comparison to the one gained through multi extrusion. The combination of high viscosity and inner friction caused by non molten granulate seem to be to the reason for this good result.

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